

State Police and the Constitutional Role of the Police in a Democratic State: The Nigerian Perspective

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Abstract:

The Nigeria police is a creation of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, and its functions are embedded in the Police Act. It is presently an agency of the federal government of Nigeria. The police are saddled with the responsibilities of preventing and detecting crime in the country. After decades of military rule, with allegations of human rights abuses, ineptitude and corruption leveled against the police, it was expected that the effectiveness of the police and its relations with the civil population would improve with the introduction of democratic governance into the country. However, the agency is still bedeviled with inefficiency, human rights violations, corrupt practices and several other problems. On the other hand, the police decry its lack of modern police technology, poor remuneration, man power challenges, shortage of weaponry and so on. One of the main positions canvassed for restructuring the police is to place it under the control of the component or federating states rather than the federal government. This work adopts the doctrinal research methodology, and is therefore, based on primary and secondary legal materials. The research recommended among other things, that there should be creation of state police; an improvement in remuneration; adequate training and retraining of police officers, and improvements in its relations with the civilian population.

Keywords: Constitution, Democracy, Nigeria, Police, State police, Human rights, Police accountability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The police in any society are a veritable tool for the prevention and detection of crime. It is an institution saddled with the responsibilities of detection, apprehension and prevention of crimes in society. It follows that the police as a law enforcement agency must be effective, transparent, and accountable in order to achieve its goal and the objective of modern and effective policing.¹ A nation that seeks to achieve greater socio-economic development and growth is bound to portray a strong and effective security base in order to minimize criminality.

When this is achieved, it heralds development and economic growth and it attracts both foreign and local investments. An unsafe society is associated with dwindling economic growth as the environment would not be suitable for investment. Regrettably, insecurity remains a pervasive problem in Nigeria. Efforts made by government to combat insecurity have not yielded good results. The perennial and deplorable security situation has culminated in the debate on the establishment of state and local police, although this position is contrary to the provisions of the constitution.² It is argued that the decentralization of the Nigeria Police would improve the security situation. Thus, it is stated that:

Proponents of state police believe that it is only a decentralization of the force as practiced in most developed countries that can rescue the nation from the precipice. Doing so will give room for the central command to focus on raising a crop of highly professional central squad that may be deployed from time to time when the need arises... with state police structure, the federating units would be able to determine their security needs and raise enough manpower to meet them...³

The above assertion is to the effect that the Nigeria police as presently constituted cannot solve or curtail the insecurity conundrum in the country except it is decentralized. Although, the call for state police has for some time been on the increase, suffice to state that the Federal Government of Nigeria seem not favourable to the decentralization of the police because it is contended that the sub-nationals (states and local governments) might use their state-controlled police to witch hunt and intimidate political opponents.

This argument does not appear to be without some credit because some state governors have used their state Independent Electoral bodies to undermine other political

¹Z.I. Mohammed and Zems Mathias, 'Effective Policing in Contemporary Nigeria; The Nigeria Police Force', (Innovative Research & Development, vol. 9(4), 2020), 1.

² See, s. 214(1) Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as Amended).

³ M.T. Nande and G.M. Awan, 'Federalism and Political Development in Nigeria' <<https://www.academia.edu/keypass>> accessed 5 March 2025.

parties in the states. This notwithstanding, the 1960/1963 Constitutions of Nigeria created regional police which was regarded as effective, although some regions did not utilize the opportunity to create their own regional police force. It must be pointed out that the advantages inherent in the establishment of states police appears to be weightier than that of the opponents as security issues are better tackled at the grassroots by those who are familiar with the environment.

Again, the Nigeria police have been found in the web of human rights abuse. It therefore, behooves on the courts to uphold the sanctity of the judiciary as the last hope of the common man. The police being a creation of the constitution ought to conform to the laws of the land and avoid arbitrary use of power and breach of the citizens' fundamental rights. Democracy presupposes the adherence to the rule of law which is to the effect that the law is supreme over any person; everyone is equal before the law; and the fundamental rights and the liberty of the people are protected at all times. The police are not above the law, so they must observe the rule of law and avoid arbitrariness which is inimical to democracy and national development. Modern policing encompasses civility and functioning within the ambit of law. Therefore, the police must adhere to the tenets of democracy and the rule of law.

2. BRIEF HISTORICAL ORIGIN OF THE NIGERIA POLICE

Historically, the Nigeria Police dates back to 1820 when the British colonial masters founded it with about 30-man strength. The police was established in other parts of Nigeria, especially the Niger Coast constabulary in 1879.⁴ In the 1890s, the Police was re-organized and a new form of police was established with modern equipment and training. The Northern and Southern Nigeria Police were set up with the amalgamation of the Lagos police and the Niger Coast Police in 1900.⁵ And in 1914, consequent upon the merger or fusion of the Northern and Southern protectorates, the Nigeria Police Force (as it was known) was formally formed.

The Nigeria Police was drastically reformed in 1920 – 1950s. However, some scholars have asserted that the Nigeria Police was formed in 1930, and it co-existed with the local police from that year to 1966.⁶ The 1960 and 1963 constitutions of Nigeria recognized regional police. The northern, western and mid-western regions created and managed their various regional police. It appeared however, that the eastern region did not utilize that opportunity, thus, there was no eastern region police. This reform introduced a rank structure and the establishment of specialized units. On attaining independence in 1960, the Nigeria police became a well-known and established institution in the country. Corruption and other challenges were noticed and faced by the police during the 1970s – 1980s. These challenges continue till date as human right

⁴ F. Adebisi, 'The Colonial Origins of the Nigerian Police' <https://folukeafrica.com/the-colonial-origins-of-the-nigerian-police/> accessed 1st July, 2024.

⁵*ibid.*

⁶ See, O.C. Okpo, F. Ntunde O., A. Anichie, 'The Nigerian Police, Safety and Public Policing: An Overview', (International Journal of Asian Science, vol. 2, No. 8, 2012), 1172.

abuses, large scale corruption and security lapses in Nigeria continue to escalate. These security lapses have heralded the exit of multinationals from the country and this has also led more to socio-economic woes.

3. DEMOCRACY AND SECURITY

Democracy is synonymous with the rule of law which presupposes that the law is supreme over any citizen; that there is equality before the law, that the rule of law guarantees fundamental rights and liberty. Rule of law therefore, guarantees checks and balances in any government.⁷ No country thrives or grows economically under civil unrest, instability and insecurity. It is therefore, the primary duty of government at all levels to ensure that the security of lives and property is guaranteed.⁸

One of the problems bedeviling the Nigerian federalism and democracy is insecurity. Apart from the security challenges from criminality such as armed robbery, internet fraud, banditry, insurgency, terrorism, kidnapping and abduction, the nation has also witnessed security confrontations through religious differences, such as religious crisis between the Christians and the Muslims, ethnic rivalries and political affiliations.

The Boko Haram sect, herders and farmers crisis, agitators and militants which include the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), and other militant or agitation groups in the Niger Delta region; the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) and the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB); the O'dua Peoples' Congress (OPC), have all employed violence to press for the actualization of their goals. Abductions for ransom have become common in the country. School children have been abducted and held for huge ransoms for long periods. An example is the kidnap of Chibok girls and 140 school children in Kaduna State.⁹ Yet under the initiative of the federal government, bandits and Boko Haram rebels were offered the option of forgiveness if they repented or abandoned the fight against the state. Bandits who surrendered were not prosecuted, but even enlisted into the army.

Abubakar Gumi, a former soldier, and Islamic cleric submitted that when states are granted autonomy, the states will tackle their challenges collectively. He proposed a National Conference, adding that a review of the 1999 Constitution would not solve Nigeria's teeming problems.¹⁰ According to Yakubu Gowon, 'when prominent beneficiaries and erstwhile champions of the unitary contortion masquerading as a

⁷ M.I.O Nwogu, 'The Rule of Law in Governance in Nigeria' (Journal of Interdisciplinary Law and Legal Issues 2010), 201.

⁸ S. 14(2) (b) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

⁹ M. Jones, 'Nigeria Kidnap: Gunmen Seize 140 School Children in Kaduna State' <<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-57636851>> accessed 3 March 2025.

¹⁰ Gumi; 'Nigeria is Disintegrating, Needs Restructuring' <<https://y25n4.app.goo.gl?link=https://www.legit.ng/1311737-gumi-talks-security-restructuring-solvenigeriasproblems.html&apn=com.naij.android&ibi=com.tutby.newsigeria&isi=830240306&ius=naij.ios>> accessed 17 March 2025.

‘Federal Republic’ voice shrill warnings of implosion and disintegration, it is time for the elite to translate angst into action and redefine Nigeria’s future’.¹¹

Former presidents of Nigeria: Yakubu Gowon and Olusegun Obasanjo warned that the eruption of the centrifugal forces could well provoke and metamorphous into another civil war, which the country might not survive because of the volatile nature and awareness of the citizens today. According to them, ‘the very foundation of the state is crumbling and unless the sensible step of remodeling it to guarantee equity, justice and local autonomy is taken, the specter of a cataclysmic collapse is real’.¹² On his part, Danjuma, like Obasanjo, a retired Army General, has warned that the country may not survive a second civil war or a religious war.¹³

The Nigeria police do not appear to have effectively discharged their constitutional role of providing internal security. Many states of the federation have resorted to the formation of their security outfits like the *Amotekun* of the South West states, to compliment the efforts of the Nigeria police in tackling the insecurity bedeviling or ravaging the country.¹⁴ A former President of the Nigerian Senate, Ahmed Ibrahim Lawan, stated that the government could not continue to play politics with security issues, adding that whether it was the federal, state or local governments or traditional rulers, the important thing is to secure the lives and properties of Nigerians.¹⁵

Also, the Southern elders and youths called upon Mohammadu Buhari (then President of Nigeria) to convoke a national summit on security as the killing and maiming of people, and the destruction of property escalated in the region.¹⁶ At the same time, the association of South-East town unions established vigilante groups to combat insecurity in Igbo land. The South-South governors also assembled to deliberate upon ways of tackling the insecurity in the country. The introduction of *Amotekun* security outfit by the South-West governors was a milestone in the fight against insecurity.¹⁷ Furthermore, the quest for security of lives and property in South-Eastern Nigeria prompted the South-East governors to establish a security outfit known as *Ebube Agu*. The reason behind the new security outfit was to oversee the activities of the local vigilante groups in the geo-political zone. The state security outfits can be seen as a continuation of the clamor for the establishment of state police despite the prohibition of state police by the constitution of Nigeria.¹⁸

¹¹See Gowon, <https://opr.as/share> , accessed 10 March 2024.

¹² See, Punch Newspaper Editorial, ‘Gowon, Obasanjo on Threat to Nigeria’s Corporate Existence’<<https://punching.com/gowon-obasanjo-on-threat-to-nigerias-corporate-existance/>>accessed 3 April 2025.

¹³ Gowon <https://opr.as/share>, accessed 10 March 2024.

¹⁴See, *Daily Independent Newspaper*, (Tuesday 8 January 2019), 1.

¹⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁶See, *The Sun Newspapers*, (Sunday 28 July 2019), 1.

¹⁷See, Amotekun: ‘Restructuring now Inevitable’, *Vanguard Newspaper* (Monday 27 January 2020), 1.

¹⁸ S.214 CFRN.

4. FUNCTIONS OF THE POLICE

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) provides that ‘the Federal Republic of Nigeria shall be a state based on the principles of democracy and social justice. It is therefore, accordingly declared that:’¹⁹

- (a) Sovereignty belongs to the people of Nigeria, from whom government through this constitution derives all its power and authority;
- (b) the security and the welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government and;
- (c) the participation by the people in their government shall be ensured in accordance with the provisions of this constitution.

The 1999 Constitution further provides that ‘the state shall also protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria.’²⁰ The fundamental rights of the citizens of Nigeria are equally embedded in the constitution²¹ and any person who alleges that ‘any of the rights guaranteed in the constitution has been is being or likely to be contravened in any state relation to him may apply to a High Court in that state for redress’.²² A High Court shall have original jurisdiction to hear and determine any application made to it in pursuance of the provisions relating to fundamental rights.

The 1999 Constitution further provides thus:²³ “there shall be a Police Force for Nigeria, which shall be known as Nigeria police, and subject to the provisions of this section, no other police shall be established for the federation or any part thereof.” The same constitution provided that:

- (a) the Nigeria police shall be organized and administered in accordance with such provisions as may be prescribed by an Act of National Assembly;
- (b) the members of the Nigeria police shall have such powers and duties as may be conferred upon them by law;
- (c) The National Assembly may make provisions for branches of the Nigeria police forming part of the armed forces of the federation or for the protection of harbors, waterways, railways, and air fields.²⁴

From the above provisions of the constitution, it is clear that it is the responsibility of government to protect the lives and property of the citizenry through the instrumentality of the police and other security agencies. The Nigeria police is a creation of the 1999

¹⁹S.14 (1) and (2) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

²⁰Ibid, s.20.

²¹Ibid, Chap. IV.

²² Ibid, s. 46.

²³ Ibid, s. 214 (1).

²⁴ Ibid, s. 214 (2) (a) – (c).

Constitution and the said constitution prohibits any state from establishing another police.²⁵ In fact, it is illegal for any state of the federation or part thereof to establish and operate a police and other security outfit contrary to the provisions of the constitution.

In consequence, the quest for the creation of State Police has been a subject of public debate. Although, the states in the Western part of Nigeria have recently established a private security outfit named 'Amotekun' for the purpose of confronting security challenges in the area, the federal government of Nigeria has warned that the Amotekun establishment is unconstitutional. Other geo-political zones in the country have indicated interest in creating similar security outfits in their regions.

The basic functions of the Police are embedded in the Police Act. The Act²⁶ provides as follows:

The police shall be employed for the prevention and detection of crime, the apprehension of offenders, the preservation of law and order; the protection of life and property and the due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which, they are directly charged, and shall perform such military duties within or without Nigeria as may be required by them by, or under the authority of, this or any other Act.

The provisions of the Police Act bestowed enormous powers upon the police. The police has a duty to protect and preserve the lives of the citizens of Nigeria; prevent and detect crimes; detect and apprehend offenders. It is the duty of the police to maintain law and order, and the police may even perform military functions such as peace keeping abroad when the need arises. The police also ensures the protection and prevention of crimes against the vulnerable; ensures respect for the rights of the citizenry; and ensures there is synergy with other security agencies in combating crime and protection of individuals. However, the courts have held that the police cannot be said to be acting in execution of their duty when they failed to comply with the law and therefore encroached on the liberty of the citizens.²⁷

Furthermore, police duties must be discharged within the ambit of law in order for the police not to incur liabilities. Thus, it was held in *Nkeiruka Okanu v Imo State C.O.P.*²⁸ that the police are not liable in the legitimate exercise of their duty and on the grounds of reasonable suspicion of having committed an offence. The police are liable for false imprisonment if the applicant or victim is able to establish that the police did not act on their own volition when they decided to arrest, or that the report was totally false, and malicious.²⁹

²⁵Ibid, s.214 (1).

²⁶See, s. 4 Police Act, Cap.359, LFN, 2020.

²⁷ See, *Onuorah v C.O.P* (1960) WNLR 110 @112.

²⁸ (2001) ICHR 407 CA411.

²⁹ See, *Nwadinobi v Bolu* (2000), CLR8 CA.

Also, the Nigeria Police have been criticized for dabbling into civil matters such as family matters, land matters, human rights issues and such other matters connected to civil causes which ought to be within the purview of civil litigations. It was held in *Umar v Abdulsalam & Ors*³⁰ that the police do not have the power to detain a person for breach of contractual obligations because it is an action totally outside their purview and legal jurisdiction. Police powers to arrest, detain and prosecute are expected to be exercised only in respect criminal issues. In *Oteri v Okorodudu*,³¹ it was held that the police have enormous power to arrest and detain a suspect upon a 'reasonable suspicion' of commission of any indictable offence. Thus, the police would have to apologize and compensate the applicant where the court found that he was unlawfully arrested.³² In certain situations, they police may have to assist the military in carrying out the duties of protecting the country from external forces. Nevertheless, the basic roles of the police include enforcing laws and maintaining peace and order.³³ Other duties include combating and preventing crime.³⁴

5. POLICING AND HUMAN RIGHTS OF THE CITIZENRY

An egalitarian society comprises of fairness, justice and adherence to the rule of law and constitutionalism, and this is synonymous with democracy. What this connotes is that everything in a democratic setting must be done within the ambit of the law. However, the rule of law and constitutionalism are irked by challenges and this has adversely affected democratic tenets and principles as liberal democracy tends to accommodate every facet of life. Again, liberal democratic tenets have created loopholes in African societies, as the norms of the African society are being eroded in order to accommodate all shades of opinion. Consequently, the rule of law is to the effect that the law itself is supreme over any individual or institution, including the police. This, will guarantee the protection of the fundamental rights and liberties of everyone.

Fundamental human rights refer to those rights that are inalienable and above the laws of the country.³⁵ They are God-given rights and no one can deprive another of such rights. In *Ezeanochie v Igwe*³⁶, the court held that the effect of the Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure Rules is that matters bothering on fundamental rights are of a greater pedestal compared to other matters. Security agencies are therefore, bound to observe the provisions of the constitution during investigations.³⁷

³⁰ (2001)1 CHR 413.

³¹ (1970)1 ANLR 194 @200.

³² See, *Okonkwo v Ogbogu* (1999) LRCN 580 (S.C); *Odogwu v A.G. Federation* (1996) 40/41 LRCN 1454 @14662.

³³ A.S. Edet, 'Crime Control and Policing the Nation States; The Nigerian Police Focus,' (International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Reviews, vol. 7, No. 2, 2017), 97.

³⁴ N.D. Ikechukwu and E.F. Ozioma 'A Critical Review of the Powers of the Nigeria Police Under the Act', (Journal of Humanities and Social Science vol. 26 issues 3 Series 4 2021), 9.

³⁵ S. 6 EFCC v Reini (2020)9 NWLR (Pt. 1730) 489 at 512.

³⁶ (2020)7 NWLR (Pt. 1724) 430 at 451.

³⁷ See S. 35 CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

In *Danfulani v EFCC*,³⁸ the court held that the police and other law enforcement agencies such as the EFCC have a duty to protect the citizens from arbitrary arrest and detention.³⁹ Therefore, the fundamental rights of citizens must be protected by security agencies in the course of their duties. In *Ajie v Iyamu & Anor*,⁴⁰ the court held that the police have no right to invade the privacy of a citizen neither can the police restrain his movement without any tangible reason or evidence. The liberties of the citizen can be restricted only within the purview of law, and only where the police have reasonable ground to suspect that the person has committed an offence.⁴¹ It is therefore, the duty of the police to ascertain that justice is not only done but must be seen to have been done.⁴² On the contrary, police actions which amount to the violations of the rights of the citizen are inimical to democracy.

6. CHALLENGES FACING THE NIGERIA POLICE

Abuse of human rights is one problem that is associated with the police in Nigeria. Although, the Inspector-General of Police disbanded the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) a few years ago, the situation has not improved as the abuse of police powers continue to date. The corrupt practices perpetrated by the Nigerian police and the failure of government to meet the demand for police reform led to the nationwide protest named 'ENDSARS' in October, 2020. The protest which was against extortion of young Nigerians by the police, led to the wanton destruction of lives and properties across the country.

Another problem confronting the Nigeria Police is poor funding. Funding of the police has been a great issue confronting the police and other security agencies, and this has led to monumental corruption in the security establishments in the country. Furthermore, criminals appear to be better armed than the police. A former Inspector-General of Police, (IGP) Mohammed Adamu, stated that criminals have more sophisticated weapons than security agencies in the country.⁴³ The former IGP opined that the increase in the number of crises in the southern part of Nigeria was connected to the proliferation of more sophisticated arms in within non-state actors. The weapons, according to the IGP are being smuggled into the country through the sea, adding that the criminals stealing crude oil and other products possess the sophisticated weapons.⁴⁴

Other problems associated with the Nigeria Police include poor remuneration, inadequate manpower, illiteracy among the personnel, inadequate training, and the

³⁸ (2016) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1493) 223.

³⁹ See also *C.O.P v Agbaje* (1969) 1 NMLR 176 at 181.

⁴⁰ (1977) BDSJ 1 at 34.

⁴¹ See *Ode v C.O.P.* (1972) NNLR 121 at 121.

⁴² See *Otufale & Ors v The State* (1968) 1 NMLR 261 at 271.

⁴³ Available on <<https://y25n4.app.goo.gl/?link=https://www.legit.ng/1304183-insecurity-criminals-sophisticated-weapons-nigeriassecurityagenciesigp.html&pn=com.naij.android&ibi=com.tutby.news.nigeriaisi=830240306&ius>> accessed 21 February 2025.

⁴⁴ *ibid.*

absence of forensic facilities in many police divisions. These challenges are faced by other security agencies which are also involved in securing the state. These include the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), the Nigerian Army, Nigeria Drug Law Enforcement Agency and others. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) was established to detect and investigate all financial crimes including Advance Fee fraud, money laundering, counterfeiting, illegal charge transfers, future market fraud, fraudulent encashment of negotiable instruments, computer credit card fraud, contract scam, among other things.⁴⁵

The proliferation of agencies charged with securing the state have created yet another challenge. Inter-agency rivalry plagues the police. As stated earlier, related agencies such as Department of States Services (DSS), Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), and the Nigerian Army (NA) discharge comparable duties, sometimes leading to conflicts among the agencies over their roles.⁴⁶ Inter-agency rivalries and conflicts have culminated in lapses on the part of the security agencies as such agencies scramble to carry out duties and functions either apportioned or not apportioned to them. The Nigeria Police and other security agencies have been accused of corruption over the years.⁴⁷ This has affected the level of confidence or trust the citizens have in security agencies.⁴⁸

The police also decry the poor state of their logistical apparatus such as operational vehicles, kits, facilities and equipment. The poor and dwindling budgetary allocations to the Nigeria Police is inadequate for the training and retraining of its personnel. Other challenges include poor remuneration, general disenchantment and poor community relations due to the high level of poverty in the country.⁴⁹ It has been noted that:

There is no doubt that personnel of the Nigeria police perform their duties in their respective spheres but it seems that some of the Nigeria Police stations and posts located in various states, local government areas, towns and villages are sometimes handicapped when it comes to discharging their duties. Certain factors hinder and undermine service delivery

⁴⁵ S. 6 EFCC Act, 2004.

⁴⁶ Channels TV, 'Military Moves to End Inter-Agency Rivalry Through Training' <https://www.channelstv.com/2024/03/20/military-moves-to-end-interagency-rival-through-training/> accessed 4 July, 2024.

⁴⁷ Corruption and Human Rights Abuses by the Nigeria Police Force <<https://www.hrw.org/report/2010/08/17,every-ones-game/corruption-and-human-rights-abuses-nigeria-police-force>> 25 February 2024.

⁴⁸ O.O. Oluwaniyi, 'Police and the Institution of Corruption in Nigeria' <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233009064_Police_and_the_institution_of_corruption_in_nigeria> accessed 3 March, 2025.

⁴⁹ G.I. Oikhala, 'The Police and Crime Management in Nigeria: Implication for National Development', (Kampala International University, Journal of Social Sciences vol. 6(1), 2020), 7.

on the part of the force which in most cases not directly the fault of the personnel of the force but of the government...⁵⁰

In order to meet the challenges confronting the police, there is a need to engage in capacity building; training, reorganization, improved funding of the police to improve their capacity to discharge their responsibilities.⁵¹

This work supports the position that canvasses for the establishment of state police; and local vigilantes within the amendments of the law. Legal measures should also be established to prevent abuse of state police by state governors and local administrators.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This work has examined the role of the police in Nigeria especially in a democratic setting. The Nigeria Police has the constitutional mandate of protecting the citizens of Nigeria, prevention and detection of crimes in Nigeria; provision of security; protection of lives and property; and to uphold the rule of law, constitutionalism and the fundamental rights and the liberty of the citizenry. Despite this core mandate, various challenges and deviations from this constitutional role have been noted. The challenges include corrupt practices, human rights abuses, poor police facilities and so on. Therefore, among other observation made, the present structure of the police whereby only the federal government controls and funds the police does not yield the best outcomes. This work therefore, supports the proponents of the establishment of state police.

⁵⁰ O. S. Agbefe, F. Ikenga and O. Atare, 'The Impact and Challenges of the Nigeria Police Force in the Maintenance of Internal Security in Nigeria,'(Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science vol. 11 – Issue 2 2023) 26 – 35.

⁵¹ I.A. Daniel, 'Intelligence Information and Policing in Nigeria: Issues and Way Forward', (The Journal of International Social Research, vol. 4(17) 2001), 475.